

INTEGRATED ANALYSIS OF COMPACTION, EDGE DISTORTION AND RESIDUAL DEFORMATION OF WIND-TURBINE THICK COMPOSITE SPAR-CAP

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ABSTRACT

A scaled model of a unidirectional glass/epoxy wind turbine spar cap measuring 7.5 mm thick was cured in a vacuum assisted oven and noticed a non-uniform thickness along its length. Even though, a vacuum pressure of 1 bar applied to the laminate, the edge deformation was severe leading to edge curvature. These shortcomings cannot be dealt separately in a single manufacturing process because of the coupled nature of the entire processing physics. Even though considerable research efforts are made to predict the process induced shape distortion and residual stress, only thermo-mechanical modeling was focused in the past. The flow-compaction induced deformation was either studied separately or not included in the numerical process modelling of deformation studies.

In this work, resin flow-induced compaction; edge distortion and residual deformation was simulated for a scaled wind turbine spar cap. For this purpose, a coupled numerical simulation procedure was established and implemented in a multi-physics finite element software package. This simulation results indicate that even though the distorted edge of the laminate is trimmed off; there will exist some curvature within the remaining part. Further, the residual deformation and related stresses can be determined from this single simulation procedure. Such fully coupled and integrated procedure may useful to select optimized process conditions to achieve intended final part dimensions with minimal manufacturing-induced effects.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, because of the requirements of large blade structures (dia. >100 m) careful attention is given to the manufacturing and integration of spars to the blade shells of a wind turbine. The spar provides the essential flexural stiffness and strength to the blades. These spars or spar caps or their flanges are either made as an integral part of the shell structure, where the shear web is then glued to the flanges, or the spars made separately and then joined to the shell structure [1, 2]. Composite materials are mostly preferred to manufacture the blades with light weight and improved performance. In specific, spar caps are manufactured from thick unidirectional (UD) GFRP laminates. Recently, CFRP laminates are explored more due to their superior flexural stiffness and strength. To improve the composite blade manufacturing efficiency and terminate blade failure problems, wind turbine industries are working hard and borrowed the best practices from the composite rotorcraft blade industry [3]. Process simulations developed in aerospace industry could be transferred to virtually verify the manufacturability and durability of the wind turbine blades. In the manufacturing perspective, the void formation, uneven fiber distribution, resin rich and poor regions, resin flash at the

edge, edge flattening, section curvature, edge distortion, fiber waviness and non-uniform thickness are some of the common issues. Among them, the section curvature and the non-uniform thickness are the major problems that affect the structural integrity and performance of the blades.

The autoclave/oven process modeling of composite materials is a coupled multi-physics problem. However, distinct numerical models are reported in the literature to simulate thermo-chemical, flow-compaction and residual stresses by ignoring one or more physics [4-17]. Initially, finite difference methods were used to solve the thermo-chemical and flow compaction models [5, 7, 18]. Later, finite element (FE) methods were introduced to solve these multi-physics problems effectively [19, 20]. Nonlinear numerical simulations also were formulated with improved material property models [12, 21]. FE control volume method was used by some researchers for the consolidation and cure of 3D composites [22]. General-purpose FE packages with user defined sub-routings were used for thermo-chemical and thermo-mechanical analysis [4, 23-25]. Heat transfer and resin flow compaction has to be solved simultaneously to update the loss of resin from the laminate at each time step in to the heat transfer analysis [14, 26, 27]. This helps to achieve a uniform compaction, void free and minimal cure induced deformation of composite laminates [28]. To date only a few researchers coupled heat transfer analysis with resin flow and compaction analysis [12, 14, 20, 22, 27], and some with residual stress calculations [21, 24]. Otherwise, the transient heat transfer, resin flow and compaction simulations were performed separately. Such simulations lead to inaccurate prediction of resin pressure distribution, compaction and cure induced deformations.

In this work, a fully coupled simulation of oven processing of a composite wind turbine spar cap was carried out. It was found that the compaction of the laminates influenced the edge curvature and the constituent level curing strains added more deformation to the composite laminates.

2 BACKGROUND

Process parameters such as cure temperature, compaction pressure, vacuum pressure, and the associated heat, mass and momentum transfer have to be optimized to enhance the quality of the laminates. A widespread theoretical and experimental work has already been done [5, 18, 29-31] towards achieving this. A complete process model consists of six inter-dependent models, such as cure kinetics, viscosity, heat transfer, resin flow, void formation, and residual stress. These are categorized into four sub models such as 1) Thermo-chemical model 2) Resin flow model 3) Deformation model 4) Void model [29]. The primary focus is to simulate the shape distortion of a cured laminate and therefore the void model is discarded in the present work.

2.1 Thermo-chemical Model

The vacuum bagged prepreg layup is cured with predefined cure temperature and pressure cycle. A convective heat transfer from the autoclave air to the laminate boundary and a conductive heat transfer with in the layup takes place. This initiates the cure reaction and the viscosity of the resin drops to a minimum. At this stage, the resin flows from the laminate to bleeder which contributes to a convective heat transfer. Further, presence of resin within the laminate generates exothermic heat through species reaction. Thus, the energy balance equation could be written as [25]

$$\rho_c c_c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho_m c_m V_D \cdot \nabla T = \nabla \cdot (k \nabla T) + \rho_m V_m Q_t \frac{d\alpha}{dt} \quad (1)$$

where ρ_m, V_m, c_m, Q_t , are the density, volume fraction, specific heat, and reaction heat per unit mass of the resin. ρ_c and c_c are the density and specific heat of the homogeneous composites respectively. Convective heat transfer may be neglected due to small resin velocities during autoclave processing [4, 23, 32].

2.2 Resin Flow and Compaction Model

By treating flow through composites as flow through porous media, at any instant of time, the normal resin velocity in the prepreg and bleeder can be denoted as [29, 33]

$$V_D = -\frac{K}{\mu} \Delta P_r \quad (2)$$

where, K is the permeability tensor and ΔP_r is the resin pressure gradient vector. This law requires permeability and resin viscosity, which are given in the Table 1. For a one dimensional consolidation with escape of resin through boundaries, the compression of resin within the pores is negligible. Thus, the stress at any point in the laminate is described as [4, 18, 20, 28, 34]

$$P_a = P_r + \sigma_f \quad (3)$$

P_a is the autoclave applied pressure, P_r is the resin pressure and σ_f is the fiber effective stress. By combining the Darcy law with effective stress compaction, the flow continuity equation is [20]

$$\frac{\partial P_r}{\partial t} = -(1 + e_0) \frac{\partial \sigma_f}{\partial e} \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{K}{\mu} \cdot \nabla P_r \right) \quad (4)$$

where, e_0 – initial void ratio and. This equation could be numerically solved to obtain the resin pressure (P_r) as a function of space and time[5].

2.3 Stress and Deformation Model

The total stress in a curing laminate could be obtained by assuming both the constituent material behavior is elastic throughout the curing process. For a symmetric laminate the total stress in any given ply is [29]

$$\sigma_i = Q_{ij}(\epsilon_j - \epsilon_R) \quad (5)$$

Q_{ij} -Modulus matrix and ϵ_j the laminate mechanical strain, a_{ij} - in plane compliance of a symmetric laminate. Johnston[35] used an incremental FE approach to simulate the residual stresses in thick composite laminates as

$$\Delta \sigma = Q_{ij}(\alpha, T, V_f) \cdot \Delta \epsilon \quad (6)$$

where $Q_{ij}(\alpha, T, V_f)$ is the instantaneous elastic modulus matrix, σ , the stress, and ϵ , the strain. Constituent level residual stresses are developed by the temperature dependent thermal expansion and cure dependent resin volume shrinkage during processing. These micro level curing strains may contribute to the macro or ply level thermal expansion mismatch, non-uniform temperature distribution and stress development at the end of curing [36, 37]. The total residual strain in a curing laminate could be written as

$$\epsilon_R = \alpha_{Tj}(T - T_a) + \epsilon_{Chj} \quad (7)$$

The thermal and cure shrinkage coefficient could be obtained from appropriate micromechanics models as given in Table 1.

Table 1: Material behavior models during cure of Glass/epoxy prepreg [7, 38, 39]

Behaviour	Model
Fibre bed permeability	$K_{11} = \frac{r_f^2}{4k_{11}} \frac{(1-v_f)^3}{v_f^2}; K_{22} = K_{33} = \frac{r_f^2}{4k_{33}} \frac{(\sqrt{\zeta_a}-1)^3}{(\zeta_a+1)}$ and $\zeta_a = \frac{V_a}{V_f}$
Fibre bed compaction	$e = \begin{cases} -5 \times 10^{-6} \sigma_f + 0.7282 & \text{for } 0 \leq \sigma_f \leq 65.378 \times 10^3 \text{ Pa} \\ -0.052 \log_{10} \sigma_f + 1.0411 & \text{for } \sigma_f > 65.378 \times 10^3 \text{ Pa} \end{cases}$
Fibre bed moduli	$E_{11f} = \frac{\pi E_f}{4 \zeta_a}; E_{22f} = \frac{3\pi E_f}{\beta^4} \frac{1}{(\sqrt{\zeta_a}-1)^4} = \frac{\sigma_f}{\epsilon_f}; G_{23f} = \frac{E_{22f}}{2(1+v_f)}$
Resin degree of cure	$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A e^{\frac{-E_a}{RT}} (1 - \alpha)^n$
Resin viscosity	$\mu = \mu_0 \exp(-E_\mu/RT + \beta\alpha)$

Resin elastic moduli	$\ln E_m = \ln E_0 + K \left\{ 1 - \left[1 - (1-n)Ae\left(\frac{E_m}{RT}\right)t \right]^{1-n} \right\} + \frac{E_{el}}{RT} \text{ for } \alpha \leq 0.99$ $E_m = 3.38 \times 10^9 \text{ for } \alpha > 0.99$
Prepreg/laminate density	$G_m = \frac{E_m}{2(1+v_m)} \text{ and } v_m = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{E_m(1-2v_m^\infty)}{E_m^\infty} \right)$ $\rho_c = \rho_f V_f + \rho_m V_m$
Prepreg/laminate specific heat	$C_c = \frac{C_f \rho_f V_f + C_m \rho_m V_m}{\rho_f V_f + \rho_m V_m}$
Effective thermal conductivity	$\frac{k_{22}}{k_m} = \frac{k_{33}}{k_m} = \left(1 - 2\sqrt{V_f/\pi} \right) + \frac{1}{B} \left[\pi - (4/F)\tan^{-1} \left(F/1 + B\sqrt{V_f/\pi} \right) \right]$ $k_{11} = V_f k_f + V_m k_m$ $B = 2 \left(\frac{k_m}{k_f} - 1 \right) \text{ and } F = \sqrt{1 - (B^2 V_f/\pi)}$
Prepreg/laminate moduli	$E_{11} = E_{11f} V_f + E_m V_m; E_{22} = E_{33} = \frac{E_{22f} E_m}{E_{22f} V_m + E_m V_f};$ $G_{12} = G_{13} = \frac{G_{12f} G_m}{G_{12f} V_m + G_m V_f}; v_{12} = v_{13} = v_{12f} V_f + V_m v_m;$ $G_{23} = \frac{G_{23f} G_m}{G_{23f} V_m + G_m V_f} \text{ and } v_{23} = \left(\frac{E_{22}}{2G_{23}} \right) - 1$
Shrinkage strain	$\varepsilon_{ch1} = \frac{\varepsilon_r E_m V_m}{E_f V_f + E_m V_m}; \varepsilon_{ch2} = (1 + v_m) \varepsilon_r V_m - \left((v_m V_m + v_f V_f) \varepsilon_{ch1} \right)$ $\text{and } \varepsilon_r = \sqrt[3]{1 + (\alpha V_{shr})} - 1$
Expansion coefficient	$\alpha_{T1} = \frac{\alpha_{1f} E_f V_f + \alpha_m E_m V_m}{E_f V_f + E_m V_m} \text{ and } \alpha_{T2} = (\alpha_{2f} + v_{12f} \alpha_{1f}) V_f + (\alpha_m + v_m \alpha_m) V_m$

3 MANUFACTURING DETAILS OF THE SCALED WIND TURBINE SPAR CAP

A scaled wind turbine blade spar cap was manufactured with the help of a specially manufactured aluminum tool. The profile of the tool was extracted from the 10 m blade profile (scaled from a 100 m blade[40]) at a station at 25% of the length. At this station, NREL S818 airfoil was used to create the blade profile shape with the chord length of 0.8 m. From this profile, the spar cap locations were identified and extracted for the length of 600 mm to design a tool as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Spar cap fabrication set up with curing oven.

A total number of 30 layers (0.25 mm each) of Glass/Epoxy prepreg were laid up on the tool and vacuum bagged with necessary accessories such as porous and non-porous peel plies and Airweave N10 bleeders. The length and thickness of the uncured lay-up were 450 mm and 7.5 mm respectively. Aluminum dams covered with bleeders were located at the edges parallel to the length of

the laminate to facilitate the resin flow (percolation flow) in in-plane transverse directions and restrict the shear flow deformations. The remaining edges normal to the length of the laminate were simply covered with bleeders to enable longitudinal flow and achieve higher fiber volume fractions. Top surface of the lay-up was also covered with bleeders to facilitate the out of plane transverse flow and remove the excessive resin from the laminate. A vacuum pressure of 1 bar is applied and cured in a convection oven with the prepreg manufacturer recommended cure cycle as given in Figure 5. The fabricated laminate is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Fabricated scaled wind turbine spar cap.

4 NUMERICAL MODELING

A commercial multi-physics software package, COMSOL, was used to perform the finite element modelling and simulation. A numerical simulation procedure was established to couple all the physics involved in fabrication of thick composites. The simulation flow diagram is given in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Schematic of the coupling between different processing physics.

Table 2: Initial and boundary conditions

Physics	Initial condition	Boundary condition (B.C.)
Heat Transfer	$T(x, y, z, t=0) = T_0 = 293.1 K$	Symmetric boundary $\rightarrow -n \cdot (-K\nabla T) = 0$ Convective boundaries $\rightarrow -n \cdot (-K\nabla T) = h \cdot (T_{cure} - T)$ with $h = 50 W/m^2K$
Degree of cure	$\alpha = 0, d\alpha/dt = 0$ for $t=0$	All the boundaries kept at zero flux
Resin flow	$P_r = P_a$ for $t=0$	Flow boundary $\rightarrow P_r = 0$ Symmetric boundary $\rightarrow -n \cdot (\rho V) = 0$
Stress-deformation	Deformation $U = 0$ and $dU/dt = 0$ for $t=0$	Bottom and symmetry side $\rightarrow n \cdot U = 0$ Top compaction $\rightarrow P_a = 100 kPa$

A quarter model of the to-be-fabricated laminate (approx. length of 250 mm) was considered for the numerical study. A quarter portion of the spar cap with imposed symmetric boundary conditions is used to simulate the deformation. The necessary initial and boundary conditions are given in Table 2. The following assumptions were made during the simulation procedure –

a) The spar cap was considered as a symmetric structure; b) The thermal properties of bagging accessories were considered as constant; c) A zero pressure boundary condition was applied by considering that the bleeders were able to absorb the entire resin that comes out of laminate; d) The thermal effect of resin in the bleeders was negligible.

Figure 4: FE discretization of the spar cap geometry interested (in meters).

The Galerkin weighted residual method was used to discretize partial differential equation of the physics. A mapped mesh of hexahedral elements was used for finite element discretization of the domain; refer Figure 4. Transversely isotropic material properties were considered for all the physics. The properties of constituent materials used in this numerical implementation are given in Tables 3.

Table 3: Constituent material properties

Property	Fiber (S2 Glass)	Resin (Epoxy)	Units
Density (ρ_f, ρ_m)	2488	1235	Kg/m ³
Specific heat (C_f, C_m)	940	2450	J/kg.K
Thermal conductivity (k_f, k_m)	1.45	0.167	W/m.K
Fiber radius (r_f)	5.8e-6	-	m
Final fiber volume fraction (V_a)	0.9	-	-
Heat of reaction (Q_t)	-	75e3	J/kg
Thermal expansion co-efficient (α_{if}, α_m)	1.6e-6	7.0e-6	1/K
Elastic modulus (E_f)	86.9e9	-	Pa
Poisson ratio (ν_f)	0.22	-	-
Volumetric shrinkage (V_{shr})	-	0.06	-
Viscosity parameters	μ_0	5.5993e-13	Pa.S
	E_μ/R	-	11683
	β	-	16.3
Cure parameters	E_α/R	-	28804
	A	-	1.14e29
	n	-	1.9
Kozeny constant	\check{k}_{11}	0.7	-
	\check{k}_{33}	0.25	-

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The corner points 2, 4, 6 and 8 and probe points 1 and 2 as shown in Figure 5 are used to plot the simulation results such as resin, fiber behavior and the deformation of the laminate during cure.

Figure 5: Locations of corner and probe points.

5.1 Resin Cure Behavior

The conversion and flow of resin during cure is the major phenomenon that dictates the total deformation of the spar cap. Initially, the resin in the prepreg was in semi-cured stage (B-stage). As the temperature increases, the resin transforms from the semisolid to liquid state and the viscosity drops to a minimum as illustrated in Figure 5 (a). At this stage, the resin moves out of the laminate towards the bleeder until gelation. This is driven by the permeability and compaction of the laminate and bleeder. After gelation the resin becomes glassy state and no further flow of resin found. Figure 5 (b) shows the degree of conversion and the modulus development of the resin. Before the cure initiates, the modulus of the B-stage resin drops to a minimum value due to the increase in cure temperature. Once the chemical reaction initiates, the modulus increases and attains a plateau at the end of cure. The increase in the modulus during the cool down was assumed to be negligible.

Figure 6: Resin cure behavior at point probe 1 (a) Viscosity (b) Degree of cure and modulus.

5.2 Fiber Bed Behavior

The effective stress in the fiber at point probe 2 due to the applied compaction/vacuum pressure is shown in Figure 7(a). It is expected to obtain a continuous non-linear curve with respect to fiber volume fraction. However, the interaction between the resin flow in longitudinal and transverse directions gives a backward shift in the fiber volume fraction at effective stresses above 65378 Pa . This is because of the different permeability's in the longitudinal and transverse directions where the

resin loss in one direction precedes the other. The permeability curves with respect to the fiber volume fraction are given in Figure 7 (b).

Figure 7: Fiber bed behavior at point probe 2 (a) Compaction (b) permeability.

5.3 Laminate Deformation during Cure

The deformation in thickness direction of the laminate at corner points 2, 4, 6 and 8 are plotted in Figure 8. At the initial stages of curing, the laminate compaction takes place due to the resin loss within minimum viscosity regions. This compaction contributes approximately 60 % to the total deformation of the laminate. The resin loss near the corner point 2 is higher because of the effect of resin outflow in all the three directions (in-plane, out of plane transverse and longitudinal). Therefore, this corner region compacts more than any other corners to a maximum deformation of *1.26 mm* at point 2.

Figure 8: Deformation in thickness direction at corner points (a) excluding cure induced effects (b) including cure induced effects.

The region near the corner point 6 has the effect of resin flow in the two transverse directions only. The resin loss near this region is less compared to near point 2. The resin remains in this regions contributes to the shear deformation of the laminate by influencing the compaction and shear modulus (G_{23}) as shown in Figure 9. Because of this edge curvature and rotation, the deformation of point 6 is in the positive directions as shown in Figure 8(b). The net deformations at point 2 and 6 confirm a non-uniform thickness along the length of the laminate. The regions near point 4 has the effect of resin flow in out of plane transverse and longitudinal directions alone. Therefore, the total deformation of point 4 is less compared to the point 2. Finally, the regions near point 8 have only the effect of out of plane transverse resin loss. The point 4 and 8 has almost the same compaction as evident in Figure 8(a)

excluding the thermal strains. This is due to the applied symmetry boundary conditions (roller support). The resin content near the edges is less compared to the center of the laminate.

Figure 9: Deformation plot normal to the length of the laminate.

The contribution of the cure shrinkage (~10 %) and the thermal shrinkage (~30%) during cool down is evident from the comparison of Figures 8(a) and 8(b). This depends on the thermal expansion and volumetric shrinkage of the constituent materials. The deformation of the laminate with respect to the change in fiber volume fraction of the laminate at point probe 2 is given in Figure 10 (a). During compaction, the deformation of the laminate is almost linear to the fiber volume fractions. After compaction, the deformation of the laminate occurs at constant volume fractions of the fiber which confirms the thermal shrinkage of the constituent materials at cool down stage. The deformation plot with fiber volume fraction distribution along the length of the laminate is shown in Figure 10 (b).

Figure 10: (a) Deformation vs Fiber volume fraction (b) Deformation along length of the laminate.

6 CONCLUSIONS

A UD composite wind turbine spar cap was fabricated in a convection oven and observed for the cure induced deformations. A non-uniform thickness along the length of the laminate was found. Further, curvatures also present in the planes normal to length of the laminate (2-3 plane), particularly, near the edges. To understand the mechanisms behind this, a coupled numerical simulation procedure was established for the fabricated spar cap of 7.5 mm thick. An integrated analysis of flow compaction, edge distortion and cure induced deformations was carried out. Only quarter portion of the model with symmetric boundary conditions was considered due to computational limitations.

The current simulation procedure was able to predict the non-uniform thickness along the length of the laminate qualitatively. This thickness change was due to the increased resin loss near the edges compared to the center of the laminate. This could be avoided by restricting the resin flow along the fiber directions with a compromise in reduced fiber volume fraction.

The regions with increased resin content affects the compaction (E_{22}) and shear modulus of the (G_{23}) laminate which gives rise to the shear deformation of the laminate. This deformation was limited by the edge dams and leads to the edge curvature in the cured part. This edge curvature could be reduced by selecting the proper permeability and thickness of the bleeder and adjusting the gap between the laminate and the edge dam. Further, the thermal expansion/shrinkage and cure shrinkage gives added deformation to the laminate.

Nevertheless, by selecting the appropriate cure temperature and pressure cycles the process induced deformations could be minimized. The current coupled simulation procedure with improved boundary conditions (including the bleeder and the fabrications accessories in the numerical model) could be used to optimize the cure cycles to reduce the process induced effects.

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